

PRACTICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE PROCESSES OF PRESCHOOL PEDAGOGICAL TEACHERS BASED ON NEURAL NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES

Maziyaeva M.E.

Teacher of the Department of Social and Humanitarian Sciences, Correspondence Department,
Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13150901>

Abstract. *This article examines in detail the practical and pedagogical aspects of the development of cognitive processes of children in a preschool educational organization based on neural network technologies. It is envisaged that special attention will be paid to the formation of motor skills in preschoolers along with the development of cognitive processes of children in a preschool educational organization. In the process of training, special attention was paid to the issues of comprehensive and deep knowledge of student's personality and taking into account his neurological capabilities. Neuropedagogical diagnostics explains the possibilities of determining the functional types of education based on the indicators of the management of a pair of human organs - hands, feet, ears and eyes.*

Keywords: *preschool educational organization, pupil, teacher, neural network, cognitive process, educational environment, development, technology.*

INTRODUCTION

Preschool education is a rapidly developing area that is in the center of attention of specialists and researchers of education around the world and in our country. The goal of state policy in the field of preschool education is to realize the right of every pupil to receive high-quality and free education. In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the diversity of forms of the modern preschool education system, the organization of the environment, flexible to the needs of society and the individual. New technologies for the development of the intellectual potential of students are appearing in preschool education. One of such technologies is the technology of neural networks.

Through education, issues of improving and comprehensively introducing a person into modern society, the level of modern knowledge, the interaction of the national and secular culture of a person are realized. All these principles are implemented in partnership, i.e. in cooperation between parents and teachers. The student satisfies his intellectual needs through education and becomes aware of the reality around him. Satisfying mental needs, students acquire skills in the process of communication in life situations and the use of various language tools.

Achieving the development of active mental activity of a child by means of mental education of preschoolers is the influence of adults with a specific purpose. Based on this influence, it is necessary to systematize the education of students about the world around them, arouse students' interest in knowledge, develop mental abilities, develop interest in knowledge, develop mental abilities, develop cognitive abilities.

Nowadays teachers of preschool educational organizations are faced with the need to rebuild the entire system of preschool education, change the methods of communication and

interaction not only with the pupil, but also with all subjects of preschool education. Therefore, the main task of teachers of a preschool educational organization is to choose innovative technologies suitable for the purpose of revealing the potential of methods and forms of correct and effective organization of work with students.

These days, our world is changing very quickly. Living and working conditions are changing, new professions and technologies are emerging as a result of scientific and technical inventions. In the modern world, it is very important for a person to constantly change, learn and discover new things throughout his or her life. It is appropriate to start preparing children, who are the future of our state, for these cardinal changes, enriching their knowledge and experience are necessary for life in the world.

Learning is one of the most complex types of human cognitive activity and, based on individual mental development, significantly accelerates the acquisition of knowledge. In the learning process, the teacher is not limited to transferring knowledge, but influences the student in this process. This makes them more active in learning, as a result, the student becomes an active participant in the educational process. Theoretical knowledge that is embedded in the minds of students during the educational process is additionally reinforced through practical activities. It is evident that a person learns the essence of the surrounding reality, things and events, encountering them in practical life and assimilating them. People comprehend the secrets of social and industrial activities, as well as the secrets of natural phenomena only through practical activities. In creating an innovative educational environment based on such education, it is effective to use the capabilities of neural network technology in creating its interactive theoretical base, general methodology, accurate diagnostic and correction technologies not only so that students remember the information given in the learning process, rather, it helps them understand and assimilate without difficulty. This condition ensures the effectiveness of students' mental activity.

Cognitive competence develops the student's ability to acquire knowledge, read and learn, independently search, analyze and select the necessary information to understand the world. They study and discover new objects in the world. They observe and experiment with others during play and interaction. Based on this experience, students discover new ways to understand problems and solve them. They share their discoveries and gradually become independent, goal-oriented, creative individuals who are able to analyze. Students can focus on solving problems, develop problem-solving strategies and use their cognitive abilities to set goals to understand and explain the world around them. As a result of maintaining interest in learning, students will acquire the skills to enjoy learning, process what they have learned and share their discoveries with others.

In the development of cognitive processes, it is very important to take into account their individual characteristics, comprehensive and deep knowledge of the personality of the learner, i.e. learners, as well as their psychophysiological characteristics, as well as their neurological capabilities and aspects based on neural network technologies. This technology is a natural mechanism for the development of the brain for cognition and learning. People naturally seek and are interested in knowledge and cognition of something. The main task of neural network technology is to better meet the educational needs of students. As a result of practical interaction of students with objects and subjects, objects affect the senses, and sensations cause perception. With the help of thinking, he has a deep understanding of reality. The process of cognition develops on the basis of practice, which is the source of knowledge.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Cognition is a complex dialectical process leading from living observation to abstract thinking and then to practice. Cognition is the process of understanding the essence of events with the help of consciousness, something abstract for a person and not mastered. Cognition of objective existence begins with its sensation. A person strives to discover the laws of nature and society and use them in his activities. The value of any theoretical knowledge is determined by how it serves practice.

Knowledge is created in the process of cognition. Knowledge is the generalized experience of people, accumulated in the process of socio-historical practice. Knowledge accurately reflects objective existence. The most accurate and perfect knowledge, in turn, is not constant, but changes in the process of social development. On the basis of knowledge, such cognitive abilities of students as observation, thinking, memory are developed, their convictions are formed, a system of ideas is formed that forms a scientific worldview.

Mental education of preschoolers is the influence of adults with a specific purpose on the development of active mental activity of the child. They include providing students with knowledge about the world around them, their systematization, awakening students' interest in learning, developing intellectual skills, developing cognitive abilities.

The process of learning, perception, understanding and thinking about the environment is different for each student. Each student's thinking is different - how the hemispheres of the brain receive information, the size and speed of work, the dominance of a particular memory system and the course of thought processes. Teachers of preschool educational organizations must take into account the peculiarities of the work of hemispheres of their brain in order to convey educational material to students in an understandable language during the educational process.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

When we talk about the general abilities of a person, we also mean the level of his development and the characteristic features of his cognitive processes, because the better they are developed in a person, the more abilities and opportunities he will have. "The cognitive process is a process that helps to learn and expand knowledge." Although both hemispheres of the human brain participate in complex cognitive processes, their work strategies differ significantly from each other. Left-hemisphere leaders are distinguished by a consistent and logical analysis of information and the direction of analysis from specific parts to the general, while right-hemisphere leaders have an intuitive and general understanding of the world and their thinking differs from the general. This situation manifests itself in the assimilation of knowledge in an intuitive-emotional (communicative) and logical-rational (non-communicative) way.

Thus, in the learning process, relying on the left hemisphere of the brain leads to the active development of only the left hemisphere, and relying on the right hemisphere of the brain leads to the active development of both hemispheres. Therefore, in the learning process, taking into account such unique aspects of the students' mentality are one of the important factors in the training, education and development of the student.

Effective implementation of these factors requires a new approach. To do this, it is necessary to combine the results of scientific research and the experience of all humanist specialists: teachers, psychologists, sociologists and neurologists. As a result of scientific and research work carried out in these areas, a new direction in pedagogy is being formed - cognitive neurobiology - neo-pedagogy.

The study of pedagogical processes from the point of view of neurological changes occurring in the human brain, that is, the synergy of neurology with pedagogy - neuropedagogy arose in 1997 as a separate science. Neuropedagogy was further developed in the general field of knowledge related to pedagogical neuropsychology, psycholinguistics, neurolinguistics, social psychology, the educational process of personality, subject and person.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the effective use of neuropedagogy and neural network methods in creating an innovative educational environment - its interactive theoretical base, general methodology, accurate diagnostic and correctional technologies - will give positive results in the field of education. It is distinguished by the fact that students are able not only to remember the information given in the educational process, but also to understand and assimilate it in an understandable form without difficulty.

Paired organs in humans - legs, arms, ears and eyes - one works better than the other, sees and hears. Which of the pair of organs moves more, this organ is called the "leading organ". In neuropedagogy, a person is taught to move a pair of organs at the same time. This requires patience from the teacher and the student.

What changes can occur in a person's life if a pair of human organs shift simultaneously. In this case, fatigue and exhaustion of a person are prevented, and the human cognitive process is forced to work more actively. That is why it is very important to teach children to make the same movements with their organs from an early age.

So, the main principle of the neuromethod is that the brain of each student is unique, the volume of reception and speed of information processing, the dominance of the memory system and the course of thought processes are different. For this reason, the process of learning, understanding and thinking of the environment of each student is fundamentally different from each other. The main task of teachers is to notice this uniqueness in each student and, based on this uniqueness, create positive results. Neuropedagogy increases the possibilities for the development of students' cognitive processes.

REFERENCES

1. State standard of preschool education and upbringing. 2022.12.12. Tashkent.
2. Preschool pedagogy F.R. Kadirova, Sh.K. Toshpolatova, N.M. Kayumova, M.N. Tashkent 2019.
3. Personal physiology and hygiene. Paul Bragg, Patricia Bragg Tashkent-2015.
3. Educational and methodological complex "Neuropedagogy". Kochkarova F.M. Andijan 2018.
5. Neuropedagogy (methodological manual) D.R.Gulamov, D.A.Mamatkulov, M.T.Akhmedova, M.H.Uumarova, M.A.Abidzhanova.